

A REVIEW ON HERBAL MOISTURIZING SOAP

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ABSTRACT

Herbal moisturizing soaps are gaining significant popularity due to their natural composition and skin-friendly properties. The present study focuses on the Preparation and evaluation of a herbal moisturizing soap using plant-based herbal ingredients such as aloe vera, neem, turmeric, coconut oil, and glycerine. These ingredients are selected for their moisturizing, antimicrobial, and nourishing effects on the skin. The soap is prepared by the process of saponification, where natural oils react with an alkali to form soap and glycerol. Herbal extracts are incorporated to enhance therapeutic benefits and reduce skin irritation caused by synthetic chemicals. The literature indicates that herbal soaps provide better hydration, improved skin texture, and minimal side effects compared to commercial chemical-based soaps. Further investigation have to be studied.

KEYWORDS: Herbal extracts, Skin condition, Saponification,

Herbal moisturing soap.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are defined as the source which are sprinkled applied or poured on the skin to improve the beautiness color & attractiveness to our skin when applied in small quantities herbal moisturizing soaps are cost effective and have no side effects to get fair skin naturally

present review article deals with the preparation and evaluation of herbal moisturizing soap for radiant skin herbal ingredients like aloe vera, neem, turmeric, coconut oil, and glycerine are used.

HERBAL INGREDIENTS USED IN MOISTURIZING SOAP

MATERIALS

Collection of Materials: The various herbal sources of Materials were collected from the medicinal garden, local super market & surroundings of Dhanvanthari institute of pharmaceutical sciences, sujathanagar, Kothagudem.

01	Turmeric	Curcuma longa		Curcuma	Anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, cancer treatment, inhibit cancer cell growth, inducing apoptosis.
02	Aloe vera	Aloe barbadensis		Aloe	Skin care, wound healing, Digestive health, oral health, anti-inflammatory, hair care, anti-microbial and cosmetics.
03	Neem powder	Azadirachta indica		Azadirachta	Insecticide, replicant, dental care, anti-viral, reduces plaque.
04	Coconut oil	Cocos nucifera		Cocos	Hydrating, skin moisturizer, hair & scalp treatment, makeup remover, dietary boost.

02. TURMERIC (CURCUMA LONGA)

Scientific name: *Curcuma longa*

Order: - Zingiberales

Genus: -Curcuma

Family: -Zingiberaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Curcuminoids: 2-5%, volatile oil: 5-10%, Polysaccharides: 10-20%, Minerals: 5-10%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Curcumin: The main active ingredient in turmeric which can make up to 5% of spice.

Demethoxycurcumin: The curcuminoid with potent anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant properties.

Volatile oils: The aroma of turmeric comes from alpha and beta turmerones and aromatic turmerones.

Therapeutic uses

ANTI-INFLAMMATORY: Turmeric contains curcumin, which has potent anti-inflammatory properties, reducing inflammation and alleviating symptoms of condition like arthritis.

ANTI OXIDANT: Turmeric curcumin as antioxidant properties, protecting against oxidative stress.

CANCER PREVENTION: Turmeric curcumin has been inhibiting cancer cell growth and inducing apoptosis.

03. ALOE VERA [ALOE BARBENDIS]

Scientificname: *Aloe*

Order: -Asparaguses

Genus: - Aloe

Family: - Liliaceae.

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Polysaccharides: 10-20%, Glyco proteins: 5-10%, Anthra quinones: 2-5%, Vitamins and minerals: 1-5%, Fatty acids: 1-5%.

Active constituents

Aloin: An anthra quinone with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant ad anti-microbial properties.

Aloe-emodin: An anthraquinone with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant ad anti-microbial properties.

Lectins: Glyco-proteins with anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties.

Therapeutic uses

SKIN CARE: - Aloe vera is used to treat various skin conditions, such as burns, wounds, eczema and acne.

COSMETIC USES: - Aloe vera is used in various cosmetic products, such as lotions, shampoos, and conditions.

ORAL HEALTH: - Aloe vera has been shown to reduce plaques, prevent tooth decay and soothe mouth ulcer.

06. NEEM POWDER

Scientific Name: *Azadirachta indica*

Order: - Sapindales

Genus: - Azadirachta

Family: - Meliaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Triterpenoids: 10-20%, Flavonoids: 5-10%, phenolic acid: 2-5%, Essential oils: 1-3%, Saponins: 1-2%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Azadirachtin: The most abundant active constituent in neem leaves.

Nimbin: A tetranortriterpenoid found in the bark of the neem plant.

Beta-Sitosterol: The polyphenolic flavonoid found in neem leaves. It has anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties.

Therapeutic uses

INSECTICIDE AND REPELLENT: Neem powder is used as a natural insecticide and repellent, effective against mosquitoes and pests.

DENTAL CARE: Neem powder is used in dental care products to reduce plaque, prevent tooth-decay and soothe mouth ulcers.

ANTI VIRAL: It is effective against various virus.

06. NEEM POWDER

Scientific Name: *Cocus nucifera*

Order: - Arecales

Genus: - Cocus

Family: - Arecaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Triterpenoids Lauric acid, myristic acid, palmitic acid, capric acid, caprylic acid, stearic acid, caproic acid, oleic acid, linoleic acid, tocopherols, phytosterols, phenolics compounds.

Therapeutic uses

Hydrating, skin moisturizer, hair & scalp treatment, makeup remover, dietary booster.

CONCLUSION

In the present scenario, people need pH Balance soaps for certain skin problems without side effects. Herbal ingredients opened the way to formulate cosmetics without any side effects. Herbal moisturizing soaps are considered as moisturizing and protective way to provide good appearance of skin. Thus, in the present work, it is very good attempt to formulate the herbal moisturizing soaps containing naturally available ingredients with less side effects which are safe and effective further investigation have to be done.

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